

8th International Conference on
Health, Treatment and Health Promotion

Health Literacy and Breast Cancer

Amirhossein Fakhre Yaseri¹

Faculty of Medicine, Qazvin University of Medical Sciences, Qazvin, Iran

Afsaneh Fallahi

Department of epidemiology, University of South Carolina, Columbia, SC, USA

Abstract

Health literacy (HL) is the ability to receive, process, and interpret health information to make decisions regarding their care. According to studies, Inadequate HL has been linked to negative health outcomes, including a lack of health information, poor mental and physical health performance, poor management of chronic diseases such as cancer. The rate of breast cancer Increased, according to statistics. In the United States After lung cancer, it is the second greatest cause of cancer-related deaths. Despite significant progress in cancer research, breast cancer remains a critical public health problem concern and the top priority in scientific research. Patients with poor HL have a difficult time understanding material that contains unfamiliar terms or concepts. Moreover, HL is considered an important element in a woman's ability to engage in health promotion and prevention activities for herself and her children. Without a good understanding of information, health care will be difficult or impossible for a woman to make informed decisions that will lead to good health outcomes for herself and her family. Numerous articles have been published on HL and its application in cancer; however, in the area of breast cancer and benefiting from health literacy, a review of breast cancer-related HL might be helpful. We review some articles regarding that and draw conclusions at the end of the session.

Keywords: Health literacy, Breast Cancer, Women

¹ Corresponding Author

8th International Conference on *Health, Treatment and Health Promotion*

Introduction:

Health literacy (HL) is the ability to receive, process, and interpret health information to make decisions regarding their care. [1] Since the 1990s, the notion of HL has gotten a lot of attention. Even though the phrase was coined in 1974, it was recommended as a critical component of health promotion until 1997. [2]

HL was included in the World Health Organization's (WHO) Health Promotion Glossary, with the following definition: Health literacy refers to the social and cognitive skills which determine an individual's motivation and ability to gain access to, understand, and use information in ways that promote and maintain good health.[3] It includes listening, reading, analyzing, and making decisions in the context of health. According to studies, Inadequate HL has been linked to negative health outcomes, including a lack of health information, poor mental and physical health performance, poor management over chronic diseases such as cancer, high hospitalization rates, high healthcare costs, and low medication adherence. [4, 5]

Cancer is a collection of complicated diseases that affects and kills millions of people throughout the world, and it has been the topic of intense investigation in both pathophysiology and therapy [6]. It is a group of disorders defined by uncontrolled cell proliferation that can penetrate and encroach on other body tissues. It is the second most common cause of death [7]. Breast cancer is still the most common cancer in women. [8]. About 1 in 8 U.S. women (approximately 13%) will develop invasive breast cancer throughout their lifetime. (Figure 1) [9]

Despite significant progress in cancer research, breast cancer remains a critical public health problem concern and the top priority in scientific research. In the United States After lung cancer, it is the second greatest cause of cancer-related deaths. [10, 11]. Although there has been a decline in breast cancer-related mortality in recent years, treatment, particularly for metastatic breast cancer, remains challenging. [12] Considering the incidence and prevalence of breast cancer, the high cost of treatment of the disease, and the fact that the disease affects young women who are economically and socially productive (around the age of 61 years) and in case of early diagnosis of the disease (screening By Mammography) This disease is one of the most treatable cancers, its importance is becoming more and more apparent. There are several risk factors for breast cancer, some of which have been proven, conflicting results, and almost ruled out. [13]

Patients with poor health literacy have a difficult time understanding material that contains unfamiliar terms or concepts. They frequently misunderstand cancer control phrases like screening, therapeutic, anatomical terms, diagnostic terms, and concepts including cure, lesion, and tumor. [14] HL is considered an important element in a woman's ability to engage in health promotion and prevention activities for herself and her children. Without a good understanding of information, health care will be difficult or impossible for a woman to make informed decisions that will lead to good health outcomes for herself and her family. With these Characteristic of measuring HL can be useful and necessary to be aware of and design special interventions to increase it, the possibility of Avoid the risks of limited literacy, as people with lower HL are more likely to assess their health as poor even after matching age, gender, race, and indicators of economic deprivation. [15] Numerous articles have been published on HL and its application in cancer; however, in the area of breast cancer and benefiting from health literacy, a review of breast cancer-related HL might be helpful.

8th International Conference on *Health, Treatment and Health Promotion*

Figure 1

Materials and Methods

This review covered the period between 1 January 1992 and 1 March 2022. Databases searched included: PubMed, Scopus, MSRT, Google Scholar, scientific SID, and BioMedCentral. We used the specified keywords to search and extract valid English articles from reliable electronic sources and by examining the complete texts of these articles, the resulting data as Described were categorized. We searched Health literacy (in titles) and Breast Cancer (in the titles and abstracts) as keywords in this study. Unrelated and duplicate items were removed. In the next step, All the remaining articles were reviewed and after removing the irrelevant items, the results related to the selected articles in the final stage were handwritten and reviewed.

Results:

Studies in cancer patients have shown that there is a relationship between poor health literacy and adverse health outcomes. The weaker the knowledge about health conditions and situations, the less use of preventive and screening services. In particular, HL levels may affect cancer outcomes. New patients may receive unknown technical information regarding a cancer diagnosis. Health professionals often involve patients in choosing treatment options. People with poor HL may not be able to acquire, process, and understand cancer information. They may also have limited access to systemic cancer care, appropriate health decisions, and practice based on health care information. Moreover, promoting health literacy plays an important role in reducing level of anxiety in patients with cancer. [16]

DeWalt et al reported poor health literacy is associated with worse mental health, such as depression. HL for women with breast cancer is one of the key points in stress management. Increasing age and disease awareness have a crucial impact on women's ability to cope with stress. [17]

People with inadequate health literacy have little knowledge of disease prevention methods and less information about disease management programs. Consequently, the success of treatments in these people decreases. People with cancer need sufficient health skills and knowledge to make informed decisions regarding a complex treatment approach, including prevention strategies, screening options, multiple treatment regimens, and participating in clinical trials. Also, cancer patients with low HL problems. Hence, poor HL is associated with reduced screening, the progress of the diagnostic phase, reduced acceptance and compliance with treatment, and reduced participation in clinical trials. [18]

Although some believe that individuals with higher health literacy may support guideline-concordant screening, the study showed that Higher HL is associated with the increased rate of screening more the recommended age. Breast

8th International Conference on
Health, Treatment and Health Promotion

cancer revealed the highest rates of screening beyond that recommended. Hence, due to the Overutilization of screening procedures, the cost of health care might increase. [19]

Poor health literacy may also affect care satisfaction. Studies have shown that breast cancer patients with low levels of HL are dissatisfied with their decision-making. [20] Although the association between HL with chemotherapy decisions was not significant in the study, patients with stage III / IV in cancer and adequate HL had a more significant role in making a decision for chemotherapy than those with inadequate HL. [21] Improved outcomes, morbidity, and healthcare utilization in breast oncology may result from a better understanding of the unique role of HL in the treatment of breast cancer patients. [22]

Based on one study, nurses should focus on health literacy, as it is highly related to the related quality of life(QOL) in survivors with breast cancer. It asserted running these programs may be one way to effect positive change in the QOL of these survivors. [23] Studies have shown the role of HL in physical activity in women with breast cancer. And revealed patients with a high level of HL do more exercise. [24]

8th International Conference on
Health, Treatment and Health Promotion

Conclusion

The results of this study showed the level of Health Literacy is a predictive factor to evaluate screening behavior in breast cancer among women. Therefore, health policymakers and health care providers should consider interventions to increase women's HL.

It is recommended that large research may be performed to clarify the impact of HL on the adoption of breast cancer preventive behaviors. The educational program should be designed regarding breast cancer by paying more attention to improving HL because one of the best ways to diagnose breast cancer earlier is improving health literacy. [25] Moreover, doctors and health care staff should evaluate the level of HL of women and based on that level explain everything such as prevention, screening, and treatment of breast cancer approaches.

8th International Conference on
Health, Treatment and Health Promotion

- [1] Kutner M, Greenberg E, Jin Y, Paulsen C. The Health Literacy of America's Adults. Results from the 2003 National Assessment of Adult Literacy. (NCES 2006-483). US Department of Education. Washington, DC: National Center for Education Statistics.
- [2] Kickbusch, I. (1997) Think health: what makes the difference? *Health Promotion International*, 12, 265–272.
- [3] World Health Organization (1998) Health Promotion Glossary. Available at: <http://www.who.int/healthpromotion/about/HPR%20Glossary%201998.pdf> (accessed 16 September 2016).
- [4] ÖZPINAR S, ÇELİK ODABAŞI N, AKYOL M. Associations between health literacy and preventive Skin Cancer Prevention Strategies among University Students. *Journal of Health Literacy*. 2020;5(3):12-25.
- [5] Izadi L, Taghdisi MH, Ghadami M, Delavar A, Sarokhani B. Identification of Effective Factors Decision Making in Crisis, in *Media rganization: A Systematic Review with Emphasis on Media literacy in Health Crisis (CORONA PANDEMIC)*. *Iranian Journal of Health Education and Health Promotion*.
- [6] U. Haberkorn, What is cancer?, *Adv. Nucl. Oncol.*, 62 (2007), pp. 1-16.
- [7] A.S. Correia, F. Gärtner, N. Vale, Drug combination and repurposing for cancer therapy: the example of breast cancer, *Heliyon*, 7 (2021), Article e05948.
- [8] F. Anjum, N. Razvi, M.A. Masood, Breast cancer therapy: a mini review, *MOJ Drug Des. Dev. Ther.*, 1 (2017), pp. 35-38.
- [9] American Cancer Society. How Common Is Breast Cancer? Jan. 2022. Available at: <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/breast-cancer/about/how-common-is-breast-cancer.html>.
- [10] M. Ávalos-Moreno, A. López-Tejada, J.L. Blaya-Cánovas, F.E. Cara, Lupiañez, A. González-González, J.A. Lorente, P. Sánchez-Rovira, S. Granados-Principal, Drug repurposing for triple-negative breast cancer, *J. Pers. Med.*, 10 (200) (2020), p. 200(2020).
- [11] Z. Anastasiadi, G.D. Lianos, E. Ignatiadou, H.V. Harissis, M. Mitsis, Breast cancer in young women: an overview, *Updates Surg.*, 69 (2017), pp. 313-317.
- [12] P.C. Lai, T.H. Chiu, YT. Huang, Overexpression of BDNF and TrkB in human bladder cancer specimens, *Oncol. Rep.*, 24 (2010).
- [13] Hasanpoor Dehkordi, A. and S.Azari(2006), Quality of life and related factor in cancer patients. *Behbood*, 10(2): 110-19.
- [14] Davis TC, Dolan N, Ferreira MR, et al. The role of inadequate health literacy skills in colorectal cancer screening. *Cancer Invest* 2001; 19:193–200.
- [15] Benjamin J, Jane V, Hayden B. (2012) Can This Patient Read and Understand Written Health Information the *Journal of the, American Medical Association*;304: 76-84.
- [16] Koay K, Schofield P, Gough K, Buchbinder R, Rischin D, Ball D, Corry J, Osborne R, Jefford M.(2016).Suboptimal health literacy in patients with lung cancer or head and neck cancer. *Supportive Care in Cancer* 6; 21: 2237-2245.
- [17] DeWalt D.A, Berkman N D, Sheridan S, Lohr K N, Pignone M P. (2004) Literacy and health outcomes. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*; 19: 1228-1239.
- [18] Davis T.C, Williams MV, Marin E, Parker R, Glass J. (2012). Health literacy and cancer communication: A cancer *Journal for Clinicians*; 52: 134-142.
- [19] Rutan MC, Sammon JD, Nguyen DD, Kilbridge KL, Herzog P, Trinh QD. The Relationship Between Health Literacy and Nonrecommended Cancer Screening. *Am J Prev Med*. 2021 Feb;60(2):e69-e72. doi: 10.1016/j.amepre.2020.08.018. Epub 2020 Dec 17. PMID: 33342672.
- [20] Adams RJ, Stocks NP, Wilson DH, Hill CL, Gravier S, Kickbusch I, et al.(2015) Health literacy--a new concept for general practice, *Aust Fam Physician*, Mar;38:144-7
- [21] Busch EL, Martin C, DeWalt DA, Sandler RS. Functional health literacy, chemotherapy decisions, and outcomes among a colorectal cancer cohort. *Cancer Control*. 2015;22:95-101.
- [22] Portelli Tremont JN, Downs-Canner S, Maduekwe U. Delving deeper into disparity: The impact of health literacy on the surgical care of breast cancer patients. *Am J Surg*. 2020 Oct;220(4):806-810.
- [23] Wei CW, Wu ML, Tung HH. Relationships between health literacy and quality of life among survivors with breast cancer. *Int J Nurs Pract*. 2021 Apr;27(2):e12922. doi: 10.1111/ijn.12922. Epub 2021 Jan 25.

8th International Conference on
Health, Treatment and Health Promotion

- [24] Plummer LC, Chalmers KA. Health literacy and physical activity in women diagnosed with breast cancer. *Psychooncology*. 2017 Oct;26(10):1478-1483.
- [25] Rakhshkhorshid M, Navaee M, Nouri N, Safarzaii F. The Association of Health Literacy with Breast Cancer Knowledge, Perception and Screening Behavior. *Eur J Breast Health*. 2018;14(3):144-147. Published 2018 Jul 1. doi:10.5152/ejbh.2018.3757.